

About

SAGROPIA is dedicated to transforming plant protection in European agriculture through the introduction of thirteen biological, low-risk pesticides, by reducing the use of some “candidates for substitution” (Cfs) and active substances.

Targeting two row crops, potato and sugar beet, the project aims to integrate sustainable solutions into comprehensive, integrated pest management (IPM) strategies in field crops.

Objectives

- Showcase the efficacy of SAGROPIA solutions and evaluate their potential for REDUCING or REPLACING Cfs pesticides.
- PROVIDE the EU agricultural sector with new, low-risk and affordable biopesticides with a known Mode of Action.
- DEVELOP and validate novel IPM strategies adapted to typical pest-disease targets.
- TEST and showcase the newly developed IPM strategies in agricultural practice in FIELD TRIALS under realistic conditions.
- ASSESS the overall environmental and socioeconomic sustainability of these novel IPM strategies.

Partners

Project Budget: €6 Million
Timeline: 01/01/2024 - 31/12/2028

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**Sustainable Agriculture
through Novel Pesticides
using an Integrated Approach**

Challenge

The European Farm to Fork (F2F) policy prioritizes food safety and security. It is targeted at reducing chemical pesticides, as their widespread use poses environmental and health risks. Row crops like potato and sugar beet face particularly high pathogen pressure, making it difficult to find alternatives to conventional and usually more hazardous plant protection products.

Solution

The project

- evaluates the performance of 13 biocontrol solutions compared to conventional chemical pesticides.
- studies their Mode of Action and toxicological profiles and seeks to develop IPM strategies that farmers can implement.
- applies a **MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH**, involving various stakeholders to ensure practical relevance and conducts small-scale field trials (across five countries over three years) to validate the most promising and scalable IPM strategies.

Approach

TARGET CROPS
Potato and sugar beet

TARGET PESTS
Blight, nematodes, insects, soil fungal pathogens

FIELD TRIALS
In 5 countries (France, Germany, the Netherlands, Poland, Switzerland)

SUBSTITUTE / REDUCE
Find alternative/reduce use of more PPPs, particularly Cfs

SYSTEM APPROACH AT IPM LEVEL
An integrated strategies approach

MULTI - ACTOR APPROACH
Stakeholder engagement, participatory trials with farmers and farmer associations

SAGROPIA SOLUTION
Economically feasible IPM strategies
Reduced environmental impact of pesticides by 50% of current usage

Impact

- **ECONOMIC:** Future-proof sugar beet and potato production and processing in Europe through cost-efficient and environmentally friendly IPM strategies, based on integrated, collaborative development of novel biological solutions.
- **SOCIETAL:** Inclusive and healthy food systems, nutrition, sustainable consumption and climate mitigation.
- **SCIENTIFIC:** Creating quality know-how, strengthening human capital in research and innovation by training and fostering the diffusion of knowledge and open-source practices.

Outcome

- Contributes to the development of novel Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies.
- Enhances our understanding of environmentally sustainable and effective pest control measures in agriculture.
- Develops a comprehensive grower's guide on best practices in sustainable pest management.
- Evaluates safety aspects, socio-economic benefits, and environmental friendliness of SAGROPIA's innovative IPM solutions.